

Aesthetic Bracket System: A Review

Review Article

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Abstract

Patients are conscious about their appearance while having orthodontic treatment as they expect a lovely smile at the completion of treatment. There is a need for optimum aesthetic appearance while undergoing orthodontic treatment. This necessity led to the development of lingual and invisible brackets. Clear aligners are popular these days as this satisfies the aesthetic concerns of the patients. As aligners are expensive, fixed appliance treatment using aesthetic brackets are preferred by major bulk of orthodontic patients. The two major aesthetic brackets include ceramic and polycarbonate brackets. The Clinical performance of aesthetic brackets has significantly improved. The strength, force control and friction of aesthetic brackets have been reduced due to improvements in bracket base design and modification of the arch wire slot.

Keywords: Aesthetic Brackets; Ceramic Brackets; Plastic Brackets.

Introduction

In recent years, the desire for improved aesthetics during fixed orthodontic therapy has spurred the development of aesthetic brackets. Orthodontic brackets are primarily chosen based on the aesthetic demands of patient. Introduction of ceramic and polycarbonate aesthetic brackets has satisfied the aesthetic demand of the patient to a greater extent. From 1986 to 1990, American Orthodontists used ceramic brackets at a rate of 5.6 % to 88.2 %, whereas polycarbonate brackets were used at a rate of 57.6 % to 24.3 %.[1]

History And Evolution Of Aesthetic Brackets

Until the early twentieth century, orthodontic bands and brackets were made of 14-18 carat gold. After World Wars I and II, however, adequate stainless steel forms were accessible. The development of tiny stainless steel brackets has become increasingly

popular. Plastic brackets were first developed in the 1970s, and they were made of acrylic at first, then polycarbonate afterwards. In the 1970s, lingual brackets were developed, which were visually superior but had significant technical issues and were time intensive for the orthodontist. Ceramic brackets first appeared in the 1980s. Invisalign was a relatively new addition to the orthodontist's toolkit. This visually pleasing method aligns teeth with a series of translucent plastic aligners. Table 1 gives the detailed history of different appliance used in orthodontics for the correction of various malocclusion.

Plastic Brackets

Plastic brackets were first launched in 1970 and were made of acrylic at first, then polycarbonate subsequently. Plastic braces were found to be more cosmetically acceptable than metal brackets by both patients and orthodontists. The inherent difficulties with these brackets were bracket discoloration, a loss of strength

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Table 1. gives the detailed history of different appliance used in orthodontics for the correction of various malocclusion.

YEAR	INVENTION
1915	Pin and Tube Appliance was invented by E. H. Angle.
	Ribbon arch appliance – modified pin and tube appliance.
1916	The term “Bracket” was first time used by E H Angle.
1951	Buonocore introduced Acid Etch technique.
1952	Holdaway introduced pre - adjusted brackets.
1950's-1960's	Ivan Lee introduced pre- torqued brackets.
1963	Cohen and Silverman introduced plastic brackets.
1968	Jaraback introduced angulated and torqued brackets for upper anteriors.
1971	Andrews introduced straight wire appliance.
1973	Lingual appliance
1976	Bio progressive technique was introduced for pre- angulated and pre- torqued brackets.
1980	Aesthetic brackets were introduced from single crystal sapphire and poly crystalline alumina.
1982	William Thomson introduced Combination Anchorage Technique(CAT) which is referred to as Modern Begg's Technique.
1987	Ceramic orthodontic brackets were introduced.
1990's	Modification of ceramic brackets and Self ligating brackets were introduced.
1994	Time brackets were introduced by Adenta.
1996	Damon S L brackets were introduced by “A” Company.
1998	Twin lock brackets were introduced by Ormco.
2000	Damon 2 brackets were introduced by “A” company and Ormco.
	In-Ovation brackets were introduced by GAC company.
2002	In-Ovation R brackets were introduced by GAC company.
	Phillippe brackets were introduced by Forestadent.
2004	Smart clip system was introduced by 3M Unitek.
2005	Sure system was introduced by Denrum.
2006	Damon 3 MX was introduced by Ormco.
	Smart clip 2 system was introduced by 3M Unitek.
	In-Ovation C system was introduced by GAC company.
2007	Clarity SL brackets were introduced by 3M Unitek.
2009	Smart clip 3 system was introduced by 3M Unitek.
2010	Cabriolet was introduced.
2011	Harmony lingual was introduced.
2012	Sensation ceramic was introduced.
2014	Bio Quick and Carrier SLX was introduced.
2015	Pro Gate I was introduced.
2016	Empower 2 was introduced.
2017	In-Ovation X and Lotus plus DS were introduced.

and stiffness, tie wing fracture, and irreversible deformation [2]. Plastic bracket binding strength was previously enhanced by chemically attaching a primer to a tooth surface [3]. These brackets' bond strengths were determined to be lower than those of metal brackets. In order to compensate for the loss of stiffness and strength, high-grade medical polyurethane brackets with fibreglass fillers or ceramic and/or metal holes, as well as high-grade medical polyurethane brackets, have been developed [4]. Although conventional polycarbonate brackets show less creep than polycarbonate brackets with metal reinforced slots, torque issues persist. Over the course of 24 hours, studies have revealed that both metal coated polycarbonate brackets and ceramic reinforced brackets lose about 15% of their torque [5] Seven widely available plastic brackets were compared to stainless steel brackets in terms of torque deformation, and it was concluded that pure polycarbonate, polyurethane, and fibreglass reinforced polycarbonate brackets distort more than metal slot reinforced plastic brackets. Under torque pressures, ceramic reinforced polycarbonate brackets showed the highest deformation [6, 7]. Self-ligating plastic brackets are a more recent development. When comparing plastic and stainless steel brackets, it was revealed that metal grooved plastic brackets are suitable for clinical use [8]. Table 2 explains about composition, prescription, slot size, special features of different plastic brackets.

Ceramic Brackets

Ceramics are materials that are formed first and then heated to solidify them. Ceramic brackets were first developed in the 1980s with improved strength, resistance to deformation and wear, colour stability, and, most importantly, a better patient appearance.

Ceramic brackets are made of either monocrystalline or polycrystalline aluminium oxide.

Specific binders were used to thermally fuse the particles together in polycrystalline ceramic brackets, while monocrystalline ceramic brackets were machined from a single sapphire crystal [9, 10] The optical clarity of the two is the most significant difference between them. Polycrystalline ceramic brackets are more translucent than monocrystalline ceramic brackets. Both monocrystalline and polycrystalline alumina exceed stainless steel in terms of hardness; however, monocrystalline alumina is significantly stronger than polycrystalline alumina, which outperforms steel in terms of tensile strength. In comparison to stainless steel, both monocrystalline and polycrystalline alumina have low fracture toughness [11]. Polycrystalline zirconia (ZrO₂) brackets, which are said to be the toughest of all ceramics, have been proposed as a replacement for alumina ceramic brackets [12]. Both stainless steel and nickel-titanium archwires have been reported to exhibit good

Table 2. Plastic Brackets.

Bracket	Composition	Prescription	Slot size	Special bonding	Special Features/ Manufacturers Claims
ESTHETIC-LINE	Composite with filler reinforcement.	Roth, Edgewise	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Primer required.	Color-clear
Alexander Spirit HMB	Slot reinforced with stainless steel.	Alexander	0.018 inch	Primer not needed.	Single tie-wing
AVALON	Polyurethane with Ag alloy.	Roth, Edgewise	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Primer not necessary.	Nickel-free slot, translucent.
BRILLIANT	Polyoxymethylene	Roth, Edgewise	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Adhesives with chemical cure is advised.	Color stability, low friction, high wear resistance.
CLASSICTM	Urethane with metal reinforcement.	Roth	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Adhesive and bonding method same as that of metal.	Nickel-free and stain-resistant.
COSMETIC BRACKETS	Polyurethane with a medical grade.	Roth	0.022 inch	Plastic primer not required.	Stain resistant.
DAMON	Surgical-grade stainless steel with clear composite resin.	Damon	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Bond enhancer and Ortho Solo universal sealant is required.	Passive self-ligating bracket.
ELATION	PET-coated polycarbonate with metal slot.	Roth	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Ideal H1 or plastic primer is advised.	High-quality transparent plastic.
ELEGANCE	Metal slotted fibre glass reinforced polycarbonate.	Roth, Edgewise	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Chemical primer is used.	Transparent composite, metal slot is fully integrated.
Envision - GOLD SLOT	Solid 18-carat gold alloy thermoplastic polyurethane slot.	Roth	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Primer not needed.	Heat treated for greater strength.
ESHELYS SERIES	Polyurethane with gold slot as optional.	Edge wise, Roth.	0.018 & 0.022 inch.	Primer not necessary.	Reduced friction.
IMAGE	Glass reinforced composite	Roth.	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Plastic primer not advised	Stain resistant.
MIURA	Plastic	Standard edge wise	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Advised primer	With or without a vertical slot-single or double wing.
OPAL	Polycrystalline polymer.	Roth	0.022 inch	Opal prime	Passive self-ligating bracket.
OYSTER ELS	Co-polymer	Roth	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Advised plastic primer.	Metal free self-ligating bracket.
Plastic Standard Edgewise Bracket	Plastic	Standard Edgewise	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Primer required	Enhanced strength via large tie wings.
POLAR AND POLAR PLUS	Medical grade polyurethane with 18-carat gold alloy slot.	Roth	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Primer not advised.	Nickel free, Injection moulded, Greater resistance.
QUANTUM	Composite	Roth	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Plastic primer needed.	Translucent in nature. Resistant to deformation and degradation.
SILKONM	Plastic with “ceramic like” filler	Roth	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Special adhesives not needed.	Injection moulded, Stain resistant surface.
SPIRIT MB	Composite	Levelling of arch, Modern treatment	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Primer not required, all adhesives can be used.	“mushroom” bonding base
SYNTHESIS COMPOSITE	Polyurethane-presence or absence of a metal slot	Edgewise, Roth	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Primer not needed.	Injection moulded followed by heat treatment to enhance strength and durability.
VOGUE	Plastic reinforced with composite.	Roth, Edgewise	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Primer not needed.	New generation plastic bracket.
WILD SPIRIT	Composite	Arch levelling, Modern treatment	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Advised Ortho Solouniversal sealant.	Unique Bonding base is unique.
ELEGANCE	Light plastic	Roth, Standard edgewise	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	Primer not needed	Anatomical base with perfect shade adaptation
SILKONPLUS BRACKETS	Injection moulded plastic material	Roth	0.018 inch 0.022 inch	No adhesive required	Superior strength and arch wire slot stability. Stain and abrasion resistant

sliding qualities, as well as clinically acceptable bond strengths, decreased plaque adhesion, and bond failure loci at the bracket/adhesive interface [13]. However, Keith et al [14] determined that zirconia brackets have no substantial advantage over polycrystalline alumina brackets in terms of frictional properties. Because alumina ceramic brackets' clinical performance has improved in recent years, zirconia brackets are no longer manufactured, and in the future, only alumina ceramic brackets will be considered.

Koutaro Maki et al. suggested a new orthodontic treatment system that uses 0.012–0.014-inch NiTi archwires and a three-slot orthodontic bracket that uses a zirconia firing working method to lubricate the interior surface of the wire slots and the external surface of the brackets. In the early stages of levelling, this system presented with a faster rate of tooth movement, and the mean

treatment time till levelling was greatly shortened [15] Table 3 explains different ceramic brackets, composition, prescription and special features of various ceramic brackets.

Properties Of Ceramic Brackets

Hardness, Tensile Strength, Fracture Toughness

Ceramic brackets exhibit high hardness because of aluminium oxide. The strength of these brackets is nine times that of stainless steel brackets.[16] Tensile strength refers to a material's ability to withstand structural failure. The tensile strength of monocrystalline alumina is higher than that of polycrystalline alumina. The tensile strength of ceramic brackets is determined by the surface condition of these brackets.[11]

Table 3. Ceramic Brackets.

Bracket	Composition	Prescription	Special features
ECLIPSE	Polycrystalline	Roth-0.018 inch&0.022 inch.	Brackets are translucent and stain resistant.
ENCORE	Polycrystalline with silver alloy slot	Roth-0.018 inch and 0.022 inch. Standard edgewise - 0.018 inch & 0.022 inch.	Braces are translucent, Mechanical retention with dove tail base.
FASCINATION2	Polycrystalline	Roth-0.018 inch and 0.022 inch. The usual standard edgewise measurements are 0.018 inch and 0.022 inch.	Translucency is optimal, Colour stability is excellent.
ILLUSION PLUS	Polycrystalline with or without silver alloy slot	Roth-0.018 inch&0.022 inch.	Brackets are translucent and stain resistant.
INTEGRA	Polycrystalline	Standard edgewise-0.018 and 0.022 inch. Roth 0.018 inch and 0.022 inch.	Transparent and stain resistant.
INSPIRE ICE	Monocrystalline e sapphire	Roth-0.018 inch&0.022 inch.	True twin brackets that are translucent in nature.
INTRIGUE	Polycrystalline	The usual edgewise thicknesses - 0.018 and 0.022 inch. Roth 0.018 inch and 0.022 inch.	Translucent, Colour coded site tabs.
INVU	Polycrystalline incorporated with polymer crystal mesh base	Standard edgewise thicknesses-0.018 and 0.022 inch. Roth- 0.018 inch and 0.022 inch. MBT-0.018 and 0.022 inch.	Twin design, Rounded arch wire slots, Debonding with ligature cutters.
LUXI II	Polycrystalline with gold insert.	Roth -0.018 inch& 0.022 inch.	Translucent, twin design, Nickel free gold slot inserts.
MONARCH	Polycrystalline	Roth-0.018 inch& 0.022 inch.	Twin wing brackets, Better rotational control,Debonding by ligature cutters.
Mxi	Polycrystalline embedded in a lattice of polymer crystals	MXi Straight-Edge -0.018 inch & 0.022 inch.	Crystal mesh base protects enamel. Debonding by ligature cutters.
MYSTIQUE	Polycrystalline	Standard Edgewise- 0.018 inch & 0.022 inch. Roth- 0.018 & 0.022 inch.	Translucent and stain resistant.
REFLECTIONS	Polycrystalline	The standard edgewise thicknesses-0.018 & 0.022 inch. Roth- 0.018 inch & 0.022 inch.	Transparent and stain resistant. Colour coded ID system.
SIGNATURE III	Polycrystalline	Roth-0.018 inch & 0.022 inch, Standard edgewise-0.018 inch & 0.022 inch.	Dovetails for mechanical retention, Easy ligation with under wing notches.
STARFIRE TMB	Monocrystalline	Roth-0.018 & 0.022 inch, Andrews-0.018 & 0.022 inch.	Clear bracket ,Straight wire aesthetic bracket.
TRANSCEND SERIES 6000	Polycrystalline	Standard edgewise -0.018 & 0.022 inch. Roth- 0.018 inch and 0.022 inch.	Microcrystalline lock base, Debonding with Transcend series 6000 debonding instrument.
VIRAGE	Polycrystalline with palladium gold alloy inserts	Roth-0.018 inch & 0.022 inch. MBT-0.018 &0.022 inch.	Resistant to stain and fracture, 100% nickel free metal slots.
20/40M	Polycrystalline	Standard edgewise -0.018 & 0.022 inch . Roth 0.018 &0.022 inch.	Strongest ceramic braces and translucent in nature.
In- Ovation R	Polycrystalline	Roth - 0.018 & 0.022inch	Low profile design, smooth curves.
In- Ovation C	Polycrystalline	Roth - 0.018 & 0.022inch	Rhodium processed clip for esthetics.
Radiance Plus	Polycrystalline	MBT-0.018 & 0.022inch Roth- 0.018 & 0.022inch	Visual placement aids (VPAS) for bonding precision and stronger tie wing radiance.
ICONIX AESTHETIC BRACES	Polycrystalline	MBT- 0.018 &0.022inch Roth - 0.018 &0.022 inch	Aesthetic champagne color, smooth zirconia finish.
3M CLARITY ADVANCED BRACKETS	Polycrystalline	MBT- 0.018 &0.022inch Roth - 0.018 &0.022 inch	Brilliant aesthetics, trusted strength & small bracket design.
DAMON CLEAR 2	Polycrystalline	MBT- 0.018 &0.022inch Roth - 0.018 &0.022 inch	Resistant to staining, precision bracket placement.
DISCOVERY PEARL	Polycrystalline	MBT- 0.018 &0.022inch Roth - 0.018 &0.022 inch	Perfect shade adaptation, anatomical base.
NEO CRYSTAL SAPPHIRE CERAMIC BRACKET SYSTEM	Monocrystalline with sapphire	MBT- 0.018 &0.022inch Roth - 0.018 &0.022 inch	Stain resistant, rounded corner, single hook
NEOLUCENT PLUS CERAMIC BRACKET SYSTEM	Monocrystalline	MBT- 0.018 &0.022inch Roth - 0.018 &0.022 inch	Crunch coat base, accurate placement with removable color coded ID mark.
OPTYC CERAMIC	Polycrystalline	MBT- 0.018 &0.022inch Roth - 0.018 &0.022 inch	Rhomboidal shape, Accu- Grip base, smooth contoured tie wings.
VELOCITY WHISPER	Polycrystalline	MBT- 0.018 &0.022inch Roth - 0.018 &0.022 inch	Ultra smooth surfaces, ample tie wing space.

Bond Strength

As ceramics have a twenty to forty times lower fracture toughness than stainless steel, shattering a ceramic bracket is easier than shattering a stainless steel bracket. Single-crystal alumina has a lower fracture toughness than polycrystalline alumina among ceramic materials.[17]

The shear bond strength of ceramic brackets is generated by the silane coupling agent at the bracket's base for mechanical retention.[16] For chemical bonding, glass is added to the aluminium oxide base and treated with a silane coupling agent. This silane coupling agent bonds to glass while leaving a free end of its mol-

ecules open for reacting with any acrylic bonding agent [16] According to numerous investigations, Stainless steel brackets have substantially lower shear bond strength than polycrystalline ceramic brackets. [18, 19].

Frictional Resistance

Ceramic brackets have been observed to create larger frictional forces than stainless steel brackets in all settings evaluated. The reduced surface roughness of metal brackets is responsible for lower frictional resistance offered by these brackets, [20] Ceramic brackets with smoother slot surfaces and ceramic brackets with metallic or ceramic/plastic slot surfaces were designed to lower the frictional resistance of ceramic brackets [21].

Base Surface Characteristics

Ceramic bracket bases are available in two different styles. The adhesive is mechanically interlocked by undercuts or grooves in one type of bracket base. These brackets may have a silane-coated surface and a flat base with grooves for mechanical attachment [22].

The other type of bracket base is flat and chemically treated to increase the binding strength. As the aluminium oxide ceramic brackets are inert, between the adhesive resin and the bracket base, a chemical mediator such as silane coupling agent is used. [23].

Polycrystalline alumina brackets with a rough base consisting of either randomly aligned sharp crystals or spherical glass particles are a recent innovation in ceramic bracket technology. These brackets only provide micromechanical interlocking with orthodontic adhesive. [24]

A ceramic bracket has been developed with a thin polycarbonate laminate on the base in an attempt to avoid enamel damage during debonding (CeramaFlex, TP Orthodontics). As a result, the enamel is adhered to the thin polycarbonate laminate rather than the ceramic substrate with an adhesive. These brackets are said to be as simple to remove as metallic brackets [25, 26].

Debonding Of Ceramic Brackets

For the debonding of ceramic brackets, many procedures have been investigated. For four commonly used methods are used: mechanical debonding, ultrasonic debonding, electrothermal debonding, and laser debonding [27].

Mechanical Debonding

Mechanical debonding uses a hand-held tool to impart mechanical force. The residues of ceramic brackets are removed with a handpiece and a diamond bur when they break during treatment or debonding. To debond these brackets from the enamel surface, ceramic bracket manufacturers recommend using specially developed debonding pliers that exert tensile or shear force. There is no obvious enamel damage when the brackets are debonded with these special pliers. This is the safest method for removing ceramic brackets and minimising enamel damage.

Ultrasonic Debonding

ultrasonic debonding employs [28] specially engineered tips to create vibrations at the bracket-adhesive contact in order to dissolve the adhesive layer between the bracket base and enamel. Originally, this process was created to remove cast metal and bridge retainers. Debonding brackets with ultrasonic debonding requires less force, which reduces bracket failure. However, the downside of this debonding technique is the longer time it takes to debond ceramic brackets, which is much longer than with the traditional method, making it uncomfortable for the patient owing to the prolonged use [29, 30].

Laser Debonding

Ceramic brackets can now be debonded with the use of a laser. Laser-induced deterioration includes thermal ablation, thermal softening, and photoablation. When the resin is heated quickly enough to achieve its vaporisation temperature before debonding, this is known as thermal ablation. Thermal softening occurs when bonding agent is heated until it softens, allowing the brackets to debond from the tooth by sliding off. This happens at relatively low laser light deposition rate. Depending on how the light energy was absorbed by these components, the resin could be heated directly or indirectly through the bracket or tooth. When the light of ultra high-energy laser reacts with the adhesive substance, photoablation happens [31] For debonding ceramic brackets, Nd:Yag and carbon dioxide lasers are commonly employed.

Electrothermal Debonding

By softening the adhesive substance, electrothermal debonding (ETD) removes the bracket with little or no force. Sheridan et al [32, 33] were the first to describe ETD for debonding ceramic brackets using cordless battery devices that generate heat that may be delivered to ceramic brackets, resulting in adhesive substance softening and bracket removal without the use of excessive effort. Bishara et al. [29] examined traditional debonding, ultrasonic debonding, and ETD advised by the manufacturer, concluding that ETD resulted in less enamel damage, bracket failure, and debonding time.

Recycling Of Ceramic Brackets

Any orthodontic bracket system that is recycled removes all adhesives from the bracket base without causing structural damage and removes any impurities created by orthodontic treatment, allowing the bracket to be rebounded to the enamel and produce a fresh adhesive bond with appropriate strength. Many manufacturers state that ceramic brackets are single-use, yet debonding causes ceramic microcracks, which can cause brackets to fail if recycled. [34]

Lew and Djeng suggested a simple chairside approach for recycling ceramic brackets, which involves heating the brackets to a cherry red colour to dissolve the adhesive from the base of the bracket [35]. To begin, remove any residual composite resin from the bracket base. Bracket should be held in place with tweezers and heated until it turns cherry red using a mini-torch. After cooling, the remnant composite resin will turn chalky white and flaky, and it can be easily scraped off the bracket base with a wax knife or gently tapped on a table top. This results in a spotless surface. After that, cool the bracket for 5 to 10 minutes until it reaches room temperature. To remove any possible residue, use

compressed air to dry it. The bracket should then be cleaned and dried in pure acetone or 100 percent isopropyl alcohol. To attach to the etched enamel surface, ceramic bracket bases have either a chemical or mechanical interlock. The silane utilised for chemical retention will be destroyed by this heating technique. On chemically treated bases, a small coating of porcelain primer should be brushed on to restore the silane layer. The primer's silane coupling agent chemically bonds the bracket base's silica component to the composite resin.

Conclusion

Ceramic and polycarbonate brackets are preferred over traditional stainless-steel brackets for patients, particularly adults, due to their improved aesthetics. Aesthetic brackets have come a long way in terms of product and clinical efficacy. The advancements in bracket base and arch wire slot design with improved manufacturing methods helped in sorting some disputes with the friction, strength, and force control of these brackets. More research and development is needed which can eventually produce aesthetic bracket that are clinically comparable to present stainless-steel brackets.

References

- [1]. Gottlieb EL, Nelson AH, Vogels DS 3rd. 1990 JCO study of orthodontic diagnosis and treatment procedures. 1. Results and trends. *J ClinOrthod.* 1991 Mar;25(3):145-56. PubMed PMID: 1939618.
- [2]. Aird JC, Durning P. Fracture of polycarbonate edgewise brackets: a clinical and SEM study. *Br J Orthod.* 1987 Jul;14(3):191-5. PubMed PMID: 3475125.
- [3]. Buzzitta VA, Hallgren SE, Powers JM. Bond strength of orthodontic direct-bonding cement-bracket systems as studied in vitro. *Am J Orthod.* 1982 Feb;81(2):87-92. PubMed PMID: 6758593.
- [4]. Alkire RG, Bagby MD, Gladwin MA, Kim H. Torsional creep of polycarbonate orthodontic brackets. *Dent Mater.* 1997 Jan;13(1):2-6. PubMed PMID: 9467316.
- [5]. Feldner JC, Sarkar NK, Sheridan JJ, Lancaster DM. In vitro torque-deformation characteristics of orthodontic polycarbonate brackets. *Am J OrthodDentofacialOrthop.* 1994 Sep;106(3):265-72. PubMed PMID: 8074091.
- [6]. Sadat-Khonsari R, Moshtaghy A, Schlegel V, Kahl-Nieke B, Möller M, Bauss O. Torque deformation characteristics of plastic brackets: a comparative study. *J OrofacOrthop.* 2004 Jan;65(1):26-33. English, German. PubMed PMID: 14749887.
- [7]. Cacciafesta V, Sfondrini MF, Ricciardi A, Scribante A, Klersy C, Auricchio F. Evaluation of friction of stainless steel and esthetic self-ligating brackets in various bracket-archwire combinations. *Am J OrthodDentofacialOrthop.* 2003 Oct;124(4):395-402. PubMed PMID: 14560269.
- [8]. Sadat-Khonsari R, Moshtaghy A, Schlegel V, Kahl-Nieke B, Möller M, Bauss O. Torque deformation characteristics of plastic brackets: a comparative study. *J OrofacOrthop.* 2004 Jan;65(1):26-33. English, German. PubMed PMID: 14749887.
- [9]. Kusy RP. Morphology of polycrystalline alumina brackets and its relationship to fracture toughness and strength. *Angle Orthod.* 1988 Jul;58(3):197-203. PubMed PMID: 3189953.
- [10]. Saunders CR, Kusy RP. Surface topography and frictional characteristics of ceramic brackets. *Am J OrthodDentofacialOrthop.* 1994 Jul;106(1):76-87. PubMed PMID: 8017353.
- [11]. Birnie D. Ceramic brackets. *Br J Orthod.* 1990 Feb;17(1):71-4. PubMed PMID: 2178681.
- [12]. Kusy RP. Orthodontic biomaterials: from the past to the present. *Angle Orthod.* 2002 Dec;72(6):501-12. PubMed PMID: 12518941.
- [13]. Springate SD, Winchester LJ. An evaluation of zirconium oxide brackets: a preliminary laboratory and clinical report. *Br J Orthod.* 1991 Aug;18(3):203-9. PubMed PMID: 1931854.
- [14]. Keith O, Kusy RP, Whitley JQ. Zirconia brackets: an evaluation of morphology and coefficients of friction. *Am J OrthodDentofacialOrthop.* 1994 Dec;106(6):605-14. PubMed PMID: 7977206.
- [15]. Maki K, Futaki K, Tanabe S, Takahashi M, Ichikawa Y, Yamaguchi T. Applicative Characteristics of a New Zirconia Bracket with Multiple Slots. *Int J Dent.* 2016;2016:4348325. PubMed PMID: 27212948.
- [16]. Swartz ML. Ceramic brackets. *J ClinOrthod.* 1988 Feb;22(2):82-8. PubMed PMID: 3075208.
- [17]. Iwasa M, Bradt RC. Fracture toughness of single-crystal alumina. *Advances in ceramics.* 1984;10:767.
- [18]. Ghafari J, Skanchy TL, Mante F. Shear bond strengths of two ceramic brackets. *J ClinOrthod.* 1992 Aug;26(8):491-3. PubMed PMID: 1452735.
- [19]. Joseph VP, Rossouw E. The shear bond strengths of stainless steel and ceramic brackets used with chemically and light-activated composite resins. *Am J OrthodDentofacialOrthop.* 1990 Feb;97(2):121-5. PubMed PMID: 2137284.
- [20]. Pratten DH, Popli K, Germane N, Gunsolley JC. Frictional resistance of ceramic and stainless steel orthodontic brackets. *Am J OrthodDentofacialOrthop.* 1990 Nov;98(5):398-403. PubMed PMID: 2239837.
- [21]. Ghafari J. Problems associated with ceramic brackets suggest limiting use to selected teeth. *Angle Orthod.* 1992 Summer;62(2):145-52. PubMed PMID: 1626749.
- [22]. Viazis AD, Cavanaugh G, Bevis RR. Bond strength of ceramic brackets under shear stress: an in vitro report. *Am J OrthodDentofacialOrthop.* 1990 Sep;98(3):214-21. PubMed PMID: 2144942.
- [23]. Swartz ML. A technical bulletin on the issue of bonding and debonding ceramic brackets. *Ormco Technical Bulletin.* 1988:1-5.
- [24]. Eliades T, Lekka M, Eliades G, Brantley WA. Surface characterization of ceramic brackets: a multitechnique approach. *Am J OrthodDentofacialOrthop.* 1994 Jan;105(1):10-8. PubMed PMID: 8291484.
- [25]. Franklin S, Garcia-Godoy F. Shear bond strengths and effects on enamel of two ceramic brackets. *J ClinOrthod.* 1993 Feb;27(2):83-8. PubMed PMID: 8496346.
- [26]. Forsberg CM, Hagberg C. Shear bond strength of ceramic brackets with chemical or mechanical retention. *Br J Orthod.* 1992 Aug;19(3):183-9. PubMed PMID: 1390574.
- [27]. Bishara SE, Fehr DE. Comparisons of the effectiveness of pliers with narrow and wide blades in debonding ceramic brackets. *Am J OrthodDentofacialOrthop.* 1993 Mar;103(3):253-7. PubMed PMID: 8456783.
- [28]. Krell KV, Jordan RD. Ultrasonic debonding of anterior etched-metal resin-bonded retainers. *Gen Dent.* 1986 Sep-Oct;34(5):378-80. PubMed PMID: 3533710.
- [29]. Bishara SE, Trulove TS. Comparisons of different debonding techniques for ceramic brackets: an in vitro study. Part I. Background and methods. *Am J OrthodDentofacialOrthop.* 1990 Aug;98(2):145-53. PubMed PMID: 2198800.
- [30]. Chen YL, Chen HY, Chiang YC, Chang HH, Lin CP. Effect of the precrack preparation with an ultrasonic instrument on the ceramic bracket removal. *J Formos Med Assoc.* 2015 Aug;114(8):704-9. PubMed PMID: 23856344.
- [31]. Tocchio RM, Williams PT, Mayer FJ, Standing KG. Laser debonding of ceramic orthodontic brackets. *Am J OrthodDentofacialOrthop.* 1993 Feb;103(2):155-62. PubMed PMID: 8427220.
- [32]. Sheridan JJ, Brawley G, Hastings J. Electrothermaldebracketing. Part I. An in vitro study. *Am J Orthod.* 1986 Jan;89(1):21-7. PubMed PMID: 3510550.
- [33]. Sheridan JJ, Brawley G, Hastings J. Electrothermaldebracketing. Part II. An in vivo study. *Am J Orthod.* 1986 Feb;89(2):141-5. PubMed PMID: 3511716.
- [34]. Martina R, Laino A, Cacciafesta V, Cantiello P. Recycling effects on ceramic brackets: a dimensional, weight and shear bond strength analysis. *Eur J Orthod.* 1997 Dec;19(6):629-36. PubMed PMID: 9458596.
- [35]. Kew KK, Djeng SK. Recycling ceramic brackets. *J ClinOrthod.* 1990 Jan;24(1):44-7. PubMed PMID: 2201696.